

**SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PROFESSIONAL
COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS OF THE DIRECTION OF HYDROLOGY
EDUCATION**

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Annation: *The article highlights the need to teach students of the direction of Hydrology education in higher education institutions to take advantage of sources on pedagogical competence and form in them visions of pedagogical competence, to introduce future teachers with theoretical knowledge on pedagogical competence, a promising direction on modernizing the educational process, to arm them with modern requirements for pedagogical competence, to ensure that the educational process.*

Base words and phrases: *competence, education, knowledge, pedagogy, profession, approach, student, teacher, upbringing, pedagogy.*

Introduction: According to scientists, one of the main ways to train specialists who meet the requirements of the times in the reform, renewal, improvement of higher education is an approach from the point of view of competence. The introduction of such a style of study and upbringing in higher education in itself requires a radical change in traditional views. It is noticeable that knowledge, skills and experiences are no longer lacking in this regard.

Modern pedagogical science and science in this regard if we look at the search, we can take a look at different fields and specialties, science and a lot of attention to Styles, teaching methods, technologies we notice that it is directed. But understanding these pedagogical methods, the issue of their use in practical activities is one of the most pressing problems it can be noted that it has become

one.

THE DEGREE OF STUDY OF THE PROBLEM.

Approach in terms of pedagogical professional competence scientific discussion among scientists and specialists from all over the world on the issue and the debate continues. In relation to pedagogical scientists from the United States and European countries, it is clear that Russian scientists left mukkas for professional competence honey. V.Slastenin, I.Isaev et al.

Chapter 3 of the teaching manual "pedagogy", written by Dedicated to the "professional competence of the educator", this concept and gives thoughts about skill. The authors say that pedagogy competence system, practical and theoretical training, professional training of an educator the profession of competence has a managerial and formative character. Management of personality formation requires competence. It is in itself summarizing the theoretical and practical training of the teacher, his demonstrates professional skills. In the direction of one profession or another teacher qualification classification pedagogical competence model they write that they are measured by their standards.[1]

V.A.Bolotov and V.V.According to the serikovs, competence from the point of view, the approach is not the student's erudition, but shows the ability to solve problems and is the first evaluates the level as a necessary ability. [2]

Ye.V.Bondorevskaya and S.V.Students in the scientific work of kulnevich the elements of competence that accumulate are only for the main purpose, pedagogical as it should be directed or necessary to carry out activities counts. [3]

V.S.Yelegina and S.M.By pokhlebaev of Russia Announcement in 3 issues of "Fundamentalnoe issledovanie " 2012 in the scientific article "Kompetentnostny podhod K organizatsii obuchenie studentov v pedagogicheskom Vuze", a student receives a creative result from his activity in the conditions of competence-oriented education and, together with this, Masters the methods, ways, methods, approaches and methods of achieving success. It is the creative result created by the student that is the creative result of the student's collaboration with the teacher. The purpose of assessing the student's appropriation is to determine the degree to which the given education is effective, which, firstly, to know the level of theoretical knowledge gained at school, and secondly, the formation of competence in it, the successful activity of the time of practice, is further accelerated. [4]

Modern, requiring deep reforms, modernization education itself considers the issue of approach in terms of competence makes transverse. It was certainly competently competently requires the preparation of the future teacher. The main purpose of Education understanding socially necessary qualities and competence in a student, self-knowledge as a person, constantly improving their knowledge, self-control forms to go and become more active.

Of course, the degree of study of this topic is considered by many foreign and conducted by higher and specialists in our country we can see in scientific research. If we are US higher pedagogical looking at the activities of the education system, B.D.Wulfson, T.N.Kurilova, Z.A.The scientific work of Malkova and others, if the USA if we want to know about the goals of pedagogical education, N.D.Nikandorova, V.Ya.Pilipovsky, professional of future teachers G. in pedagogical education.G.Agapova, O.O.Borovikova, V.S.Budenko and the work of others, the system of professional development of us teachers and about V.B.Gargay, N.I.A look at the work of Kustinova and others if we throw, it will be desirable. Named above from the scientific work of scientists, the educational system of Russia and the United States is divided into we can imagine that it is enriched by filling. USA, Canada, Pedagogical staff in Australia and a number of European countries creation of a continuous system of preparation.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The word” competence “is formed from the Latin word” competere“, which in translation means” competent“,” to be worthy”. When” competence ” is said, the level of awareness of an individual from one field to another, knowledge of that field, is understood. The scientific-theoretical foundations of pedagogical competence, the content and essence of the concept of competence and the formation of deep pedagogical-psychological training in relation to competence in the teaching and education of students in the system of innovative processes in education are considered important.

In the manner of discussion, it should be said that to teach students to use resources related to pedagogical competence and form in them visions of pedagogical competence, to ensure that future teachers acquire the necessary cognitive skills to organize the educational process taking into account the child's psyche, its neuropsychological, neuropedagogical capabilities, to introduce theoretical knowledge on pedagogical competence, to it consists in the formation of literacy and deep pedagogical – psychological training in relation to competence.[5]

Pedagogical competence is formed in interaction with a number of disciplines: theory and history of pedagogy, pedagogical conflict, neuropedagogy, pedagogical imidjalogy, innovative pedagogical technologies, psychology of young Times, social pedagogy, edagogic Axiology, pedagogical psychology.

It is a requirement of the period to achieve educational efficiency through a new vision and implementation of the educational system, Rich in complex, laborious, unexpected situations, but considered a necessary need of society, the effective application of innovative pedagogical and Informational Technologies in the course of the lesson. A graduate of an educational institution can enter into personal, social, economic and professional relationships in his life, take his place in society, face the potential of mainly pedagogical personnel is a decisive factor in ensuring that the solution of problems, and most importantly, is competitive in its field, profession.

CONCLUSION

It is clear from the above that the profession of students of the direction of Hydrology education in higher educational institutions that the issue of competence continues a number of controversies over the issue of its place in society. In the field of education, the analysis of the main universal elements of competence is one of the most fundamental problems of modern pedagogy. In the case of basic competence, there is a wide variety of opinions on the application of the experience

of Educators of the world or on the setting of competence criteria based on the norms of traditional Uzbek pedagogy, only those issues that have not yet been solved.

Education is the main condition and pledge of human perfection and prosperity of the nation. Educational processes are a nationwide issue of state control. In our country, education, that is, teaching, is carried out in harmony with upbringing. While the National Training Program requires a radical improvement in the educational process, it is conspicuous that the training of competent educators is also approached based on these requirements. Competence or extreme skillfulness, the training of highly qualified educators has become the most pressing issue of our time, and, it is permissible to say, the most fundamental task of the state and society.

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